
UNVEILING STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS, CHALLENGES AND EXPERIENCE IN LEARNING ANATOMY AMONG HEALTH SCIENCES STUDENTS IN AL-HIKMAH UNIVERSITY, ILORIN, NIGERIA

This questionnaire gathers students' perceptions, challenges, and recommendations related to learning anatomy in higher education at Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Nigeria. Participation is voluntary, and responses are confidential and will be aggregated for review and improvement of anatomy education.

Target Population: Undergraduate students studying B.Sc. Anatomy, Medicine, Medical Laboratory Science, Nursing, Physiology, and Public Health at Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Nigeria.

* Indicates required question

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION

This section collects basic information about your background and learning experience to help understand how individual differences influence perceptions about Anatomy learning. Please select the most appropriate options.

1.

Gender *

(Mark only one)

- Male
 Female
-

2.

Marital Status *

(Mark only one)

- Single
 Married
 Divorced / Separated
 Widowed
-

3.

Age range *

(Mark only one)

- <18
 18–20
 21–24
 25–29
 ≥30
-

4.

Programme of study *

(Select all that apply)

- Anatomy
- Medicine
- Medical Laboratory Science
- Nursing
- Physiology
- Physiotherapy
- Public Health

5.

Level of study *

(Mark only one)

- 200 Level
- 300 Level
- 400 Level
- 500 Level
- 600 Level

6.

Institution *

(Mark only one)

- Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin
- Other (please specify): _____

7.

Extent of exposure to anatomy classes/practicals *

(Mark only one)

- Minimal (1 semester)
- Moderate (2–3 semesters)
- Extensive (more than 3 semesters)

SECTION B: STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF LEARNING ANATOMY

This section explores how participants feel about studying Anatomy, including their sense of fulfilment, motivation, and how they perceive its relevance to future career opportunities.

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = Strongly Agree

9.

Anatomy provides essential foundational knowledge for understanding the human body and disease processes. *

Strongly Disagree

- (1) (2) (3) (4) (5)

Strongly Agree

10.

Learning anatomy is intellectually meaningful rather than purely memorization-based. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

11.

Anatomy positively influences my confidence as a medical/allied health sciences student. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

12.

I can clearly see the relevance of anatomy to my current or future professional role. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

13.

Anatomy learning supports the development of my clinical or applied reasoning skills. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

14.

Studying anatomy has contributed to my professional identity as a future health professional. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

15.

Anatomy lecturers are approachable and supportive in enhancing student learning. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

16.

My experience learning anatomy has been satisfactory. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

SECTION D: CHALLENGES EXPERIENCED IN LEARNING ANATOMY

This section explores the main challenges that may limit participants' understanding, performance, and motivation in studying anatomy. Your honest responses will help identify areas for improvement in teaching and learning.

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = Strongly Agree

17.

The volume and complexity of anatomy content are overwhelming. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

18.

Anatomy learning often places excessive emphasis on memorization. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

19.

Limited access to cadavers, models, and high-quality visual resources affects my learning. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

20.

Anatomy practical sessions are often overcrowded or insufficient in duration. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

21.

It is difficult to integrate anatomy knowledge with clinical and applied contexts. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

22.

Feedback and academic support in anatomy courses are often inadequate. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

23.

Resource limitations reduce the quality of anatomy education in my institution. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

SECTION E: STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF CADAVERIC DISSECTION

This section aims to gather your views about learning anatomy through cadaveric dissection, including how it affects your engagement, understanding, and skill development.

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = Strongly Agree

24.

Dissecting cadavers helps me understand anatomy concepts more clearly. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

25.

Working with cadavers improves my ability to visualize organs and body systems. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

26.

Cadaver-based learning helps me remember anatomy better and perform well in exams. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

27.

Hands-on dissection strengthens my practical and clinical skills. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

28.

Dissection improves my spatial understanding of anatomical structures. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

29.

Cadaver-based learning provides real-life experience that cannot be achieved from virtual resources. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

30.

Dissection sessions are interesting, engaging, and enjoyable. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

31.

Learning anatomy through cadavers feels challenging in a way that supports growth.

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

32.

Cadaver-based learning is not frightening or physically uncomfortable.

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

33.

Cadaver-based learning is a valuable part of anatomy education.

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

SECTION F: STUDENTS' PERCEPTIONS OF VIRTUAL RESOURCES IN ANATOMY LEARNING

This section seeks to understand your experiences using virtual resources for anatomy learning. Virtual resources include tools such as 3D anatomy applications, virtual dissection software, online tutorials, simulation platforms, and other digital learning tools. We are interested in how these tools affect your understanding, skill development, engagement, and overall learning experience.

Scale: 1 = Strongly Disagree 2 = Disagree 3 = Neutral 4 = Agree 5 = Strongly Agree

34.

Tools such as 3D anatomy applications, virtual dissection software, or AI-based platforms enhance understanding of anatomical structures compared to traditional methods. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

35.

Integrating virtual resources into anatomy education increases students' confidence in their knowledge and skills. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

36.

Digital platforms improve visualization of anatomical structures, helping to understand different body compartments and layers. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

37.

Virtual anatomy resources make learning anatomy less stressful and enjoyable. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

38.

Virtual resources offer flexibility, allowing students to study at their own pace and convenience. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

39.

Virtual resources allow repeated practice and review, improving retention and application of anatomy knowledge. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

40.

Digital tools provide interactive simulations of clinical or pathological scenarios that cadaveric sessions cannot replicate. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

41.

Combining cadaveric dissection with virtual resources would enhance the understanding and retention of anatomy concepts. *

Strongly Disagree

 1 2 3 4 5

Strongly Agree

SECTION G: OPEN-ENDED QUESTIONS

This section invites participants to share thoughts, suggestions, and experiences that may provide insight into improving anatomy teaching and learning. Your honest responses will help identify areas for enhancement and best practices.

42.

How would you describe your overall experience of learning anatomy? *

43.

What do you expect anatomy education to provide that is currently lacking? *

44.

What aspects of anatomy learning do you find most challenging? *

45.

How can anatomy education be improved to better support your learning, skills development, and overall educational experience?

46.

What barriers or challenges do you face in adopting virtual resources for learning anatomy?

Thank you for your participation. Your responses are strictly confidential and will be used solely for academic research purposes.
Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Nigeria · Department of Anatomy